

**ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY
LEVEL STUDENTS
(MAHESHWAR AND MANDLESHWAR. DIST. KHARGON (M.P.))**

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INTRODUCTION

Environment is, in general terms, a surrounding or condition influencing development and growth of all the living beings.

For the last several decades nature and environment have always been a source of human reflection and investigation as the environmental pollution has reached to such a critical stage that we find ourselves passing through an irreversible climate change and are not able to retrieve the previous climate back.

Now the liability lies on the next generation and I am sure that environmental awareness among the senior secondary students will lead the next generation towards restraining the unstoppable environmental changes.

It can be said that environmental education is education through environment, about environment and for environment. It is both a style and subject – matter of education. In so far as the style is concerned, it means teaching for environment that include components and issues such as controlling the environment, establishing proper ecological equilibrium which entails proper use and conservation of resources and also involves control of environment is not only functionally useful but is also aesthetically enjoyable.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following objectives are set forth in the present study:

- To know the level of knowledge and compare environmental awareness among students of government and public schools.
- To compare environmental awareness among male students belonging to government and public schools.
- To compare environmental awareness among female students of governmental and public schools.
- To compare environmental awareness among students of arts and science groups of government schools.
- To compare environmental awareness among students of art and science groups of public schools.
- To compare environmental awareness among high and low achieving students.

- To compare environmental awareness among students who have and don't have an access to media.

RESEARCH METHOD

The development of the problem for the present study has been traced in the light of theoretical and research background and the following steps of method and procedure adopted in conducting the study.

1. Design of the study

Under a broad canvas of survey method of research a questionnaire is made for survey.

2. Selection of sample

The design of the study consisted in taking a representative sample of 160 (80 from govt. schools and 80 from public schools) students at +2 level from various schools of Maheshwar and Mandleshwar.

3. Tools used

Appropriate tool i.e. "Environment Awareness Ability Measure Test" by Praveen Kumar Jha is used for checking awareness towards environment.

4. Procedure of Data Collection

The test has 51 items (including 43 positively and 8 negatively worded). A numerical weightage of 1 is assigned to the category agree in case of positive items and disagree in the case of negative items.

To collect the data the investigator visited the various schools of Maheshwar and Mandleshwar personally.

5. Statistical treatment

The data were analyzed with help of suitable statistical techniques like mean, Standard Deviation (SD), Standard Error of Mean and t-ratio.

The following formulas were used to find out...

$$M (\text{Mean}) = \sum X/N, SD (\sigma = \sqrt{\sum X^2/N})$$

SAMPLE SELECTION

A sample consisted of 160 students (80 from Government schools and 80 from Public Schools) at + 2 level equally divided on the basis of sex and academic stream was taken.

List of the School Surveyed:

1. Govt. Boys Sr. Secondary School, Maheshwar
2. Govt. Girls Sr. Secondary School, Mandleshwar
3. Kanwartara Sr. Secondary School, Mandleshwar
4. St. Paul Sr. Secondary School, Mandleshwar

FINDING

The main findings are added here under:

1. There is no significant difference on environmental awareness among students of public and govt. schools.
2. There is no significant difference on environmental awareness among male students of government and public school at Sr. Secondary level.

3. There is no significant difference on environmental awareness among male students of government and public schools at Sr. Secondary level.
4. The science students are significantly higher than arts students of govt. schools. Science students are more aware about environmental problems in comparison to arts students.
5. The science students are significantly higher than arts students of public schools. Science students are more aware about environmental problems in comparison to arts students.
6. Students with 60% marks (high achieving) are more enlightened than the average students getting marks in the range of 50-60%.
7. The high achieving students are significantly higher than low achieving students on EAAM.
8. There is no significant difference on environmental awareness among average achieving and low achieving students.
9. There is no significant difference among students who have an access to media and those who do not have an access to media.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the above given findings the following conclusions may be drawn.

1. Students of Govt. and public schools have similar environmental awareness ability.
2. Male and Female students of govt. and public schools have similar environmental awareness ability.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings of the study are of crucial importance in protecting environment, However, some of its practical implications can be pooled together to consider its importance. On the basis of the finding of the study, the following implications emerge out:

1. To enhance the chances of creating more awareness about the environment, the education process has to play more a practical role.
2. The subject of environmental education should be included as compulsory subject in curriculum.
3. Special emphasis should be given on students at lower school level because they are tomorrow's citizens and educating those means education a generation.
4. For creating environmental awareness among students and general public, various campaigns can be launched from time to time. In school, essay writing competition, painting competition, debates, on the topic of environment can organized.
5. The causes of environmental pollution should be brought of the notice of the children so that remedial measure can be taken.
6. Environmental education should be made more effective in rural areas.
7. Students can contribute significantly in conserving the environment.